

What's In A Word: The Damage Of The Abstract In War

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Abstract: Using the initial ideas of Terry Jones of Monty Python and U.S. historian Marilyn B. Young, this paper challenges the use of the abstract in security problems and debates. As Jones states, can you fight and win against an abstract noun? In his case, it was the then-ongoing War on Terror. Jones expands on this idea further, stating that such abstraction has the potential to lead to 'forever wars' as, in this case,

terrorism can never be defeated. The re-establishment of direct language based on the greater use of proper nouns exemplifies clarity. Precision in language is not a panacea to strategic issues, but it is the only way to start.

Bottom-line-up-front: The present-day strategic language, at least in the public domain, has drifted far too long in the use of abstract terms. Clarity in the language of strategy is and always will be vital. This discipline needs to be rediscovered.

Problem statement: How does abstraction in public language impact clarity and accountability in security situations?

So what?: Clarity and accountability will improve by avoiding the abstract in security language. As Winston Churchill put it, 'precision in language leads to precision in execution.' The world is becoming far too dangerous a place for anything else. It is important to, therefore, look at two aspects of this: first, in terms of strategy to end the era of strategic innocence and greater focus on the context of a specific conflict, and second, to learn more from the language of strategic failure of the last twenty or so years.

Uncertainty Rather Than Security

'New Leviathans are fostering uncertainty rather than creating security.' – Andy Owens.[1]

George Orwell clearly defined the relationship of language with power in his landmark novel *1984*.^[2] In his case, the restriction of meaning and the acceptance of absolute falsehoods led to uncritical compliance. Media control of the type in 'Orwell's Oceania' is more difficult in present-day society due to the decentralised distribution provided by the internet. However, this does not dissipate the power of language in skewing and undermining security issues. The present-day threat is not language restriction but rather the use of the 'abstract' in the security language. The late Terry Jones masterfully articulated this problem. Terry Jones asks us: can you fight and win against an abstract noun?

In Jones' case, his focus was the then-ongoing War on Terror. He asked, how does one know when either side has won? When does 'terror' surrender? One could ask the same question about the War on Drugs,^[3] the War on Cancer (the medical equivalent of Vietnam^[4]) or even the War on Want.^[5] This

paper will not deal with the militarisation of social issues but rather the damage such abstraction does to strategy. The paper will ask if abstract expression is another gateway to Marilyn B. Young's 'forever wars' and other malaise.[6] She, along with Terry Jones, was not alone in such concerns.[7]

Although Jones concedes that a war was fought against fascism, he urges readers to note that this threat was embodied by Nazi Germany, with the clear outcome of unconditional surrender. Fascism itself has not been defeated. Abstract nouns have a horrible habit of having a rather long existence. Never will they change; never will they be defeated. Perhaps equally insidiously, they are malleable to all manner of 'threats' that assist in lobbying additional funding for a security agency (missile gaps being just one example).[8] The War on Terror was used cynically to push a neo-conservative agenda into the Middle East through the invasion of Iraq to seek non-existent weapons of mass destruction[9] (another vague phrase). 'Nation building' is another such vague term, and incidentally, it is something military organisations are neither organised for nor, as recent evidence would indicate, particularly good at.[10]

War, Special Military Operation, Hybrid War – What is it?

Public security dialogue seems to be unable to break this addiction to abstraction. There are now two belligerent major powers flexing military force actively and passively, namely, Russia and China. Russia is conducting a 'special military operation' in Ukraine, and China is an expert practitioner in 'grey zone' conflict or 'hybrid war'. In fact, Russia has started a specific national and cultural annihilation war through a military invasion. Meanwhile, China seeks to expand its political and financial status through (for now) age-old practices of subterfuge and intimidation[11] short of bloody violence.[12] In contrast, Ukrainian President Volodymyr Zelensky, bearing the brunt of invasion, has been rather concrete in his demands;[13] fighting for survival tends to have this effect.

Aside from horribly muddying security debate with pages and pages of semantics and shifting definitions, abstraction in conflict has another security issue. That of allowing defence departments to over-blow threats. This is perhaps not so much of a risk in present-day Europe, particularly the Baltic states, which carry deep historical scars. However, in the corridor of the U.S. government, the need to hype a particular threat based on data that later proves to be erroneous has occurred numerous times.[14] Five hundred (or 600[15]) ship navies and wars on two fronts constantly reappear.[16] There

is no mention of how and what for, just a declaration of some gap or possible scenario, never accurately quantified or given a rigorous assessment of likelihood.[17]

Jones was likewise profoundly concerned about the open nature of the wars on abstract nouns, as was the distinguished scholar Mary B. Phillips. Her concerns extended into other abstractions, such as Dean Acheson's formation of the 'great crescent' to justify the 'police action' in Korea in the 1950s. There is now a similar geographically bizarre abstraction in the form of the European 'Indo-Pacific tilt,' which seems to go only so far as a vague lean by sending small detachments far from home for a few months or not at all.[18] Strategic abstractions are somewhat fragile in their encounter with maps, especially when Europe's geographic backyard is ablaze.

In a similar vein down under, further compounding a particular Australian addiction to the abstract, the nation's defence force is now apparently into 'impactful projection,' with an appropriately loose technical definition[19] — the abstract technical 'silver bullet' to conflict resolution more dangerous to the author than the enemy.

Highlighting such dangers, Young raises another concern about the abstraction of the 'War against Terror'; in her case, how to eliminate a tactic? Jones, likewise, also questions this along the lines of inconsistent responses to tactics. He asks why, after the horrendous bombing of Hyde and Regent's Park in 1982, the UK did not seek to attack the primary source of funds for the IRA (the U.S.) or the training areas in Ireland. This idea was, of course, a mental exercise in the absurd. Still, it is important to show how the abstract could lead to unaccountable military freewheeling, contradictions, and hypocrisy. To dismiss this with the wave of a hand and say, 'Well, whatever means necessary!' is the road to perdition — one of body counts and forever wars.[20]

Proxy has become another abstraction connected to war, struggling for a precise definition and being used at times in the same inflammatory fashion as terrorism.[21] Alliances may lend too much accountability for major powers. The recent abandonment of Afghan people resisting the Taliban, and the Kurds fighting the Syrian Army and ISIS (note the proper nouns), would indicate that Western nations are inferior practitioners of proxy warfare.

So What?

So, what to do? For instance, in the case of the Russia-Ukraine War in particular, instead of repeating the phrase 'special military operation', a more accurate statement is: 'Russia is at war with Ukraine. So far, its stated aim is the elimination of self-determination for Ukrainians and re-absorption of the land and people back into itself; Russia has offered no other credible option for resolution and continuously attempts to deter support by the hollow threat of nuclear weapon release.' Such a relatively concrete definition/overview of the security situation is likely to make strategizing for a solution much easier. The same effect would occur in addressing security concerns related to China, a similarly concrete assessment could be as follows: 'China's belligerence through aggressive precursor drug production,[22] diplomatic coercion,[23] resource control[24] and creeping territorial expansion[25] under a deeply autocratic leader requires restraint.'

Precise language itself does not prevent conflict either. But one can hope that the examples above help reveal the benefit of avoiding abstraction and generalisation. Defining security threats or challenges concretely at least helps in gaining initial clarity, which is critical in security planning and would genuinely assist public debate. Moreover, it prevents us from casually using the most serious of words — War.

Mary Ticktin looks at the political and sociological impact that the use of 'innocence' brings in turning the concrete into indefinite, marginalising and over-simplifying the 'innocent' group or person being considered.[26] Removing context, abstract language allows in strategy also this disempowerment to occur. It is, therefore, necessary to end this long period era of accepting strategic innocence in security discourse.

The innocence must end both in terms of no longer accepting vague language in security policy and, as importantly, acknowledging, as Colin Gray has put it, "*there are always thugs, villains, rogues, and fools out there as well as some in here, who mean us harm.*"[27] Importantly, understanding that, as he further says, "*the contexts of war are all important*". Gray goes on to define seven contexts, namely, political, social-cultural, technological, military-strategic, geopolitical and geostrategic, and historical.[28] Phrasing such as 'grey zone', 'missile gap', 'wars on', or 'unnamed proxies,' deny context, and, worse, allow Gray's internal fools to hide their true intent.

The use of the abstract in security dialogue has fuelled two major wars, where, in the case of the Iraq invasion, the primary strategic beneficiary was the prime U.S. regional opponent, Iran;[29] and the War in Afghanistan failed not only in destroying Al Qaeda and Osama Bin Laden but also in return the deposed regime.[30] Indeed, the language of the Afghanistan conflict was one of obfuscation and falsehoods.[31] Some who knew better continued as 'expert' sideline commentators on the Russian-Ukrainian War.[32] So, the second step is to look back harder and analyse how those wars' language masked abject failure. As Marilyn B. Young, Neil Sheehan, and Hannah Arendt did so well in writing about the Vietnam War.[33] Looking into the future, beyond the modern rephrasing (abstraction) of 'traditional' threats, the prior treatment of climate change by some as an abstract issue has now led to at least two lost decades of mitigating effort — something we will now pay dearly for. Again, something that should be scrutinised now, not ex post facto.

Similarly, as Andy Owens has stated in his fine book review of John Gray's recent work, the ship of state, or at least many that steer it, feeds on this ambiguity. Colin Gray was primarily a strategist of the state-based conflict. Still, he was prescient in identifying this risk of internal self-deception. The presumption that Western democratic systems are somehow immune to Orwellian deception is misplaced; it has just arrived in a different form — a surplus of vague phrases rather than a constriction of language. Many leaders seem to have woken up to this fact as a clear danger has presented itself. But not all leaders. Therefore, there is a need to determine how this occurred and to avoid repetition. Crucially, the benefits of the discipline of expression require rediscovery; "*Precision in language leads to precision in execution.*"[34]

Clarity with aforethought does not mean the answers will not be messy, untidy, and imperfect; that is the nature of conflict, but correct orientation is vital.[35] In the case of strategy, abstraction is as powerful a threat as the enemy itself. The world is now too dangerous a place for the waste and misdirection abstraction engenders.

"If language is not correct, then what is said is not what is meant; if what is said is not what is meant, then what must be done remains undone" – Confucius[36]

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